

The Place of Adult Education in Enhancing the Delivery of Relief Services to Emergency Victims in Kano State, Nigeria

By

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Abstract

This paper is entitled place of adult education in enhancing the delivery of relief services to emergency victims in Kano State, Nigeria. The focus of the paper is to examine the categories of emergency victims in Kano State from 2010 to 2019; determine the immediate needs of emergency victims; examine the relief services provided to different categories of emergency victims, and determine the challenges faced by Kano State Emergency Management Agency in the delivery of relief services to the emergency victims. Using the survey research methodology, 390 sampled subjects were drawn from a population of 52,661. This was based on the table for determining sample size by Krejcie and Morgan (2006). 30 Officials of KSEMA and 360 emergency victims were used purposively. Two self-developed instruments were used in collection of data. These were a Questionnaire and a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guide. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by experts and its reliability was obtained using the split-half method in which the reliability coefficient level of 0.084 was obtained. Data was analysed qualitatively and in descriptive statistics. Findings of the study includes; the categories of emergency victims in Kano State from the year 2010 to 2019 were victims of fire disaster; victims of flooding; victims of insurgency; victims of community conflict; victims of drought; victims of election violence; victims of armed robbery, and victims of automobile accidents, and the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State were security of lives and properties; comfortable shelter; essential food stuff; adequate medical facilities;

reconstructions; sufficient monetary donations; adequate family welfare; counselling support; relationship building; livelihood activities, and spiritual needs to address social, economic, and psychological challenges. Among the recommendations made to address the challenges facing the delivery of relief services includes; KSEMA should reconsider active community involvement as priority in finding sufficient resources that will cater for the immediate needs of the emergency victims, and Kano State Government should establish agencies that will be charge with the managing of emergency situations at all the local government levels in the State.

Keywords: Disaster, Emergency, Knowledge Economy, Management, Relief, and Victim.

Introduction

The development of “Knowledge Economy Society” has over decade necessitated adult education as an academic discipline to bring innovations in all human endeavours. Contemporarily, adult education is no longer a discipline focusing on the provision of literacy education alone. But it basically concerns with provision of services meant for rehabilitation and empowerment of various individuals and communities whom might have experienced various forms of emergency situations. Adult education in Nigeria was for long been engaged in the undertaking of various programmes at various academic fields and specializations in the academic arena. A part from women education, civic right education, youth empowerment education etc, social welfare and social work education were among the new discoveries made by adult education through knowledge economy. While the social welfare services were provided for the general well-being of the public which include; education, health, housing, transportation, security, and food security to mention few, there are other services provided to special categories of individuals expose to various personal, social, and psychological problems within the context of emergency situations. Most of graduates of adult education programmes at various institutions of leaning in Nigeria have now become familiar with the relevance of social welfare and social work education to the academic field of adult education.

Relief service is a social work process organized for the purpose of helping individuals and groups facing various social problems such as earthquake, volcanoes, storms, fire outbreaks, insurgencies, flood, drought, desertification, and other forms of catastrophe requiring emergency responses.

In Kano State therefore, there is the Kano State Emergency Management Agency (KSEMA) which was established in March 1999 by the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) Act No. 12 of 1999 and as amended by the Act No.50 of 1999 to manage disasters in all its ramifications.

Based on this background, it has been observed that Kano State government through emergency management agency has been providing relief materials and services meant for the rehabilitation of emergency victims. This paper therefore determines the relief services provided to emergency victims by KSEMA in Kano State and find out the challenges faced by the agency in the delivery of the relief services.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study will focus on various concepts such as relief services, disaster, emergency management, and emergency victims.

Concept of Relief Services

Relief is an assistance provided to disadvantaged individuals who experienced difficulties that require emergency responses. Relief services however are programs which aim to assist people in distressful situations such as earthquake, volcanoes, drought, flood, fire outbreak, various forms of crises, etc. Many programs are provided by various institutions so as to help the victims of disasters to deal with their immediate crises or situations in a way that maintains the dignity of the individual and encourages self reliance amongst them. These assistance through services or rehabilitative may take the form of purchase vouchers (for food, utilities, transport, or pharmaceuticals), food parcels,

and cash to support payment of rent or bills, and sometimes other items such as clothing and household goods. Relief services involves programmes and infrastructure which required additional funding from other sources, such as donations, state/territory and local government funding, specialist service funding, and charitable trust funding (ACOSS, 2003). Relief service therefore entails a range variety of supply of goods, services, and programmes which are meant to serve people whom experience various forms of distressful situations. The responses made are regarded as interventional measures to control or in other words reduces the vulnerability of such victims of disasters or otherwise.

Concept of Disaster

Disaster is a condition or situation of significant destruction, disruption and/or distress to a community. The extent to which a community's condition is worsened by a disaster is relative to its pre-disaster condition. Several actions undertaken by officials in disaster management that support this goal both pre-disaster (to forestall or reduce potential damage) and post-disaster (to recover from actual damage), and perfectly these activities would reduce the potential effects of a disaster to the point of elimination. Yet the very nature of disasters makes this ideal unachievable. There are five major characteristics of disasters that make them hard to surmount (for a more detailed explanation, see Donahue and Joyce, 2001; Waugh, 2000):

1. Disasters are large, rapid-onset incidents relative to the size and resources of an affected jurisdiction.
2. Disasters are uncertain with respect to both their occurrences and their outcomes.
3. Risks and benefits are difficult to assess and compare.
4. Disasters are dynamic events develop as they progress, and they transform in response to human actions and natural forces.

5. Disasters are relatively rare because most communities experience few, if any, disasters during the average time in office of a political official or the average time of residence of a citizen.

In tropical regions, cases of flooding of high magnitude that have resulted in serious consequences have been caused by heavy rain or thunderstorms, hurricanes, snow melt and dam failures (Jeb & Aggarwal, 2008). In some other countries, flood has also caused land degradation due to low-lying coastal areas and river flood plains (Abbas, 2008). Nigeria as a country is not left out in the menace of flooding. According to Folorunsho and Awosika (2001) and Adebayo (2011), flood is no longer a new phenomenon in Nigeria and its destructive tendencies are sometimes enormous.

Concept of Emergency Management

Emergency is an event, actual or imminent, which endangers or threatens to endanger life, property or the environment, and which requires a significant and coordinated response. Intervention to address disasters has evolved through time into a complex policy subsystem, and disaster policy is implemented through a set of functions known as emergency management and response. Modern approaches to emergency management and response involve multidimensional efforts to reduce our vulnerability to hazards; to diminish the impact of disasters; and to prepare for, respond to, and recover from those that occur.

Concept of Emergency Victim

Emergency victim is a two word name given to a person who suffered the effect of occurrence of disaster/event that disturbs the well-being in terms of loss of property, wealth, and psychological stability. Emergency are sudden occurrences of events that immensely affect the lives of people requiring an immediate response (Godwin and Paul, 2018). Therefore, the concept of emergency

victim can be viewed as an individual or group of people who experienced disastrous situations which led to loss of life, property, or general well-being.

Statement of the Problem

The phenomenon relief service has been considered by social workers as an intervention provided to victims who experience natural disasters and other disasters caused by human beings. The development of the provision of relief as a service was the consequent of higher increase of emergency victims needing social, economic, and psychological assistance so as to reduce vulnerability among them. In the decade 2010-2019, human civilization has witnessed many catastrophes that have resulted into the displacement of people across continents, countries, states and communities. On January 21, 2012 Kano State started witnessing several Boko-Haram attacks in places like: the Police Headquarters Bompai; the Zonal Headquarters KofarNa'isa, and the SSS Headquarters at Badawa. This has led to death of various policemen, and innocent people. The Convoy of the Late Emir of Kano on 19th January, 2013; the Kano Central Mosque on 28th November, 2014, the Farm Centre GSM markets, Sabongari and Kwari markets. Fire out-breaks in places like: Schools, Petrol Stations, Dawanau, Kurmi, Kwari, Sabongari, and Farm Centre GSM market; Flooding in Bagwai, Wudil, Minjibir, Kibiya, Bunkure, and Kura local government areas. Many people lost their lives, some were injured and needed medical assistance, some lost their arms, legs and became crippled, women and children lost their husbands and became homeless roaming and participate in begging in the streets in Kano. Various victims were found vulnerable to various social, economic, and psychological problems such as crime, poverty, hunger, hopelessness, frustration, prostitution, unemployment, insecurity and many other social vices that can facilitate abnormality of victims in Kano State. The SEMA in Kano State was backed-up by an enabling law to act as disaster management structure to formulate and implement policies that enhances the well-being of victims

in such emergency situations. Goods worth millions of Naira were provided to various categories of emergency victims. The aim of these was to enhance quality of life and improve the well-being of the emergency victims in Kano State. It is in the light of this, that, the researcher intended to conduct a study so as to assess the challenges facing the delivery of relief services to emergency victims, in so doing, the study ought to find ways in addressing the challenges facing the delivery of relief services to emergency victims through resource allocation in a knowledge economy society: Lessons from Emergency Management Agency Kano State, Nigeria:

The Knowledge Economy

The knowledge economy according to Širá, Vavrek, Kravčáková, Vozárová, and Kotulič (2020) is not just an imaginary concept, but a contemporary, which has an essential difference from the era of agrarian and industrial economies. Although it appeared only in the early 1990s, it has by now had an impact and caused changes in all spheres of economic and social life, and this influence is continuously growing. The trend of development of a knowledge economy is the formation of a knowledge economy society, which means the onset of a new stage in the development of the global economy. The idea of a knowledge-based economy dates to the 1990s. The primary objective of knowledge-based economy society was for European countries to catch up with America in technological development (Širá, et al, 2020). However, the issues of sustainable development and the knowledge economy are two directions of development to which most countries of the world, including EU Member States, draw attention. Nevertheless most of countries face steady changes in scientific and technical development, but there are also new modern trends in the way they do business. Every member in this global market is required to adapt its activities to these fast changes. Countries struggle to increase their level of development depending on the available resources. However, in Nigeria where development was dependent on availability of resources which are

limited, great effort should also be used in the context of meeting the needs of future generations. Nowadays, the process of sustainable development is well in line with the process of developing the knowledge economy. To achieve the appropriate changes, the two processes need to be harmonized. The knowledge economy as a possible way to transform society to achieve sustainable economic growth as well as to solve the various climate challenges arising from the growing scarcity of resources. But it is noted that there are challenges facing the delivery of relief services which will not make the knowledge economy a reality. The prospects now are to find out the ways to address these challenges through resources allocation in a knowledge economy society.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to examine the place of adult education in enhancing the delivery of relief services to emergency victims in Kano State, Nigeria. Other specific objectives are:

- I. To examine the categories of emergency victims in Kano State from 2010 to 2019;
- ii. To determine the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State;
- iii. To examine the relief services provided to different categories of emergency victims by Kano State Emergency Management Agency, and
- iv. To determine the challenges faced by Kano State Emergency Management Agency in the delivery of relief services to the emergency victims.

Research Questions

The study answered the following research questions:

- I. What are the categories of emergency victims in Kano State from 2010 to 2019?
- ii. What are the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State?
- iii. What are the relief services provided to different categories of emergency victims by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?
- iv. What are the challenges faced by Kano State Emergency Management Agency in the delivery of relief services to the emergency victims?

Methodology

This study adopted a survey research design over a population comprising of 287 staffs and 52,374 emergency victims benefitted from the relief services provided by SEMA in Kano State. Out of the 52,661 subjects who served as population for this study, 381 were selected and involved in the study as sample. This was based on the table for determining sample size by Krejcie and Morgan (2006). However, in order to improve the precision of findings and reduce sampling error, the researcher used three hundred and ninety 390 as sample for this study. The sampling procedure used in this study was a purposive sampling procedure. In this study therefore, the researcher deliberately selected and involved 30 Officials of KSEMA and 360 emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services of KSEMA within the year 2010-2019 purposively. However, in reaching out to the sampled beneficiaries a snowball technique was used. Two self-developed instruments were used in collection of data. These were a Questionnaire and a Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Guide. While a modified 4-point Likert Scale Questionnaire named “Questionnaire for Emergency Victims of KSEMA” (QEVKSEMA) for the emergency victims was used, an FGD was conducted with Officials of KSEMA who were involved in the delivery of the relief services. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by expert in Measurement and Evaluation; a professional in social welfare, and a specialist in emergency management. And the reliability of the instruments was obtained using the split-half method in which the reliability coefficient level of 0.084 was obtained. Data was analyzed in two forms, that is qualitatively and through descriptive statistics using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23. While the data collected through the FGD with the staff involved in the delivery of relief services provided to emergency victims by KSEMA was reported verbatim and discussed qualitatively, the SPSS software was installed on to a Microsoft laptop computer and programmed to process the data collected from the emergency victims who benefitted from the relief services of KSEMA. The data retrieved was presented in simple frequency

(F) and percentage (%), mean (X) as well as cumulative mean score that indicated a decision from the analysis. While a cumulative mean above 2.50 justified the acceptance of statements in the items of the questionnaire, any cumulative mean below 2.50 justified the rejections of statements in the items of the questionnaire.

Results

Research question 1: What are the categories of emergency victims in Kano State from 2010 to 2019?

This research question was answered by the staffs of KSEMA whom were involved in the FGD conducted with the researcher. The FGD conducted indicated that:

“The categories of emergency victims whom benefitted from the relief service offered by the KSEMA from the year 2010 to 2019 were “victims of fire disaster; victims of flooding; victims of insurgency; victims of community conflict; victims of drought; victims of election violence; victims of armed robbery, and victims of automobile accident”.

Research question 2: What are the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State?

This research question was answered by the sampled emergency victims in simple frequency counts, percentages, mean score, and cumulative mean; where n=347.

Table 1. The immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State

Immediate needs	SA		A		D		SD		X
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Security of life and property	188	54.2	81	23.3	36	10.4	42	12.1	3.1960
Comfortable shelter	158	45.5	116	33.4	32	9.2	41	11.8	3.1268
Provision of essential food stuff	172	49.6	106	30.5	39	11.2	30	8.6	3.2104
Provision of adequate medical facilities	129	37.2	127	36.6	57	16.4	34	9.8	3.0115
Reconstruction	87	25.1	145	41.8	65	18.7	50	14.4	2.7752
Provision of sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare to emergency victims	105	30.3	158	45.5	34	9.8	50	14.4	2.9164
Provision of counselling support needs to address traumatic experience	73	21.0	176	50.7	65	18.7	33	9.5	2.8329
Provision of relationship building support needs to address social isolation	81	23.3	177	51.0	53	15.3	36	10.4	2.8732
Provision of livelihood activities support needs to address economic challenges	98	28.2	167	48.1	40	11.5	42	12.1	2.9251
Provision of spiritual needs to address social life changes	89	25.6	120	34.6	80	23.1	58	16.7	2.6916
Cumulative mean= 2.9559									

Table 1 above described the statements on the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State. According to the table, responses on the statement on security of life and property of the respondents were strongly agreed by 54.2% of the sampled respondents. This was followed by 23.3% of the respondents who agreed with the said statement on security of life and property. When the statement on comfortable shelter as an immediate need of the emergency victims was stated, 45.5% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement. This was followed by 33.4% of the respondents who opined that comfortable shelter was an immediate need of emergency victims. However, respondents whom strongly agreed that provision of essential food stuff was an immediate need of emergency victims constituted 49.6%. This was followed by a reasonable percentage of 30.5 whom agreed with

the said statement. Regarding the statement that the provision of adequate medical facilities was an immediate need of emergency victims, respondents whom strongly agreed and those agreed with the statement were closely having the sound percentages of 37.2 and 36.6. These were followed by the respondents whom disagreed with the said statement constituted 16.4%. Furthermore, 41.8% of the sampled respondents agreed with the statement that reconstruction was an immediate need of emergency victims. This was however followed by 25.1% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with said statement. Looking in to the table, it is observed that highest percentage 45.5 of the respondents agreed with the statement that provision of sufficient monetary donation and adequate family welfare was an immediate need of the emergency victims. This was followed by 30.3% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. It has been observed that 50.7% of the respondents agreed with the statement that provision of counselling support needs to address traumatic experience were an immediate need of emergency victims. This was complemented by 21% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. In addition to this were 51% of the respondents whom agreed with the statement that provision of relationship building support needs to address social isolation were the immediate needs of emergency victims. This was followed by 23.3% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. Moreover, 48.1% of the respondents agreed with the statement that provision of livelihood activities support needs to address economic challenges were the immediate needs of emergency victims. Only 28.2% of the respondents strongly agreed with the said statement. While 25.6% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that provision of spiritual needs to address social life challenges were the immediate needs of emergency victims, highest percentage of 34.6 agreed with the statement. These statements on the immediate needs of emergency victims were considered accepted by the respondents as justified by the cumulative mean score of 2.9559 higher than the decision rule of 2.5000 in favour of the acceptance of the statement provided in the items of the questionnaire.

Research question 3: What are the relief services provided to categories of emergency victims by Kano State Emergency Management Agency?

This research question was answered by the sampled emergency victims in simple frequency counts, percentages, mean score, and cumulative mean; where n=347.

Table 2. The relief services provided to categories of emergency victims by Kano State Emergency Management Agency

Opinions of emergency victims on relief services	SA		A		D		SD		X
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Provision of counselling services	82	23.6	179	51.6	44	12.7	42	12.1	2.8674
Provision of housing	94	27.1	163	47.0	39	11.2	51	14.7	2.8646
Provision of food items	101	29.1	164	47.3	49	14.1	33	9.5	2.9597
Provision of home utensils	68	19.6	122	35.2	105	30.3	52	15.0	2.9937
Provision of clothing materials	70	20.2	183	52.7	55	15.9	39	11.2	2.8184
Provision of building materials	147	42.4	122	35.2	37	10.7	41	11.8	3.0807
Provision of medical facilities	84	24.2	165	47.6	55	15.9	43	12.4	2.8357
Provision of agricultural facilities	161	46.4	88	25.4	51	14.7	47	13.5	3.0461
Provision of capacity building materials	172	49.6	84	24.2	46	13.3	45	13.0	3.1037
Provision of monetary donation	126	36.3	84	24.2	87	25.1	50	14.4	2.8242
Cumulative mean= 2.8994									

Table 2 above is on the opinion of the sampled emergency victims whom benefitted from the relief services provided by KSEMA in Kano. From this table, it was observed that 51.6% of the respondents agreed with the statement that provision of counselling services was a relief service provided to the categories of emergency victims. This was followed by 23.6% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. However, the highest percentage of 47 agreed with the statement that provision housing was a relief service provided to the categories of emergency victims. This was followed by 27.1% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement. In addition to this were those 47.3% of the

respondents whom agreed with the statement that provision of food items were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims. 27.1% of the respondents strongly agreed with the said statement. It was also observed from the table that 19.6% of the sampled respondents strongly agreed that provision of home utensils were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims. The highest percentage of 35.2 of the respondents agreed with the said statement. Furthermore, respondents whom strongly agreed with the statement that provision of clothing materials were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims constituted 20.2%. These were complemented with the highest percentage of 52.7 respondents whom agreed with the said statement. From this table also, respondents whom strongly agreed with the statement that provision of building materials were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims constituted 42.4%. These were followed by 35.2% of the respondents whom agreed with the said statement. Added to these were respondents constituted 47.6% whom agreed with the statement that provision of medical facilities were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims. This was followed by 24.2% of the respondents whom strongly agreed with the said statement on provision of medical facilities. Moreover, the highest percentage of 49.6 were those respondents whom strongly agreed with the statement that provision of capacity building materials were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims. This was followed by 24.2% of the respondents whom agreed with the said statement. Also 36.3% of the respondents strongly agreed with the statement that that provision of monetary donation were the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims. It is observed that 24.2% of the respondents agreed with the said statement. These statements on the opinions of emergency victims regarding the relief services provided to the categories of emergency victims were accepted by the respondents. This was justified by a cumulative mean score of 2.8994 higher than the decision rule of 2.5000 in favour of the items in the questionnaire.

Research question 4: What are the challenges faced by Kano State Emergency Management Agency in the delivery of relief services to emergency victims?

This research question was answered by the staffs of KSEMA whom were involved in the FGD conducted with the researcher on the challenges faced in the delivery of relief services to emergency victims by Kano State Emergency Management Agency. According to the FGD, most of the participated members during the sessions justified that:

“The major challenges reported by the staffs were administrative bureaucracy; inadequate funding by the State government; inadequate external funding; lack of communal participation; poor internal donation; poor distribution channel; lack of emergency management agency at the local government level, and frequent occurrence of emergency situations in the State.”

Followed by these are the other challenges faced by the emergency victims as described by some of the members during the FGD sessions, which included “illiteracy; political affiliations; increase in the rate of the emergency victims; lack of disaster preparedness skills; and communal apathy”.

Summary of Findings

From the proceeding analysis the following findings were deduced:

- i) The categories of emergency victims in Kano State from the year 2010 to 2019 were victims of fire disaster; victims of flooding; victims of insurgency; victims of community conflict; victims of drought; victims of election violence; victims of armed robbery, and victims of automobile accidents.
- ii) The immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State were security of lives and properties; comfortable shelter; essential food stuff; adequate medical facilities; reconstructions; sufficient monetary donations; adequate family welfare; counselling support; relationship building; livelihood activities, and spiritual needs to address social, economic, and psychological challenges.
- iii) The opinions of emergency victims on the relief services provision were provisions of counselling services; housing; food items; home utensils; clothing materials; building materials; medical facilities; agricultural facilities; capacity building materials, and monetary donation.
- iv) The challenges faced by KSEMA in the delivery of relief services to emergency victims were administrative bureaucracy; inadequate funding by the State government; inadequate external funding; lack of communal participation; poor internal donation; poor distribution channel; lack of emergency management agency at the local government level, and frequent occurrence of emergency situations in the State.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding of this study revealed that the categories of emergency victims in Kano State from the year 2010 to 2019 were victims of fire disaster; victims of flooding; victims of insurgency; victims of community conflict; victims of drought; victims of election violence; victims of armed

robbery, and victims of automobile accidents. This finding was similar with most of the findings of various studies conducted on emergency victims, disaster awareness, preparedness, and management. These were however justified in studies by Obikaeze, & Onuoha, (2016) entitled the Nigerian-State and Management of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPS) from 2012-2016; Aminu, (2018) entitled Social Welfare Need of and Care for Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Kumbotso Local Government Area, Kano State.

The second finding of this study on the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kano State was related to the findings of the studies conducted by Aminu (2018). This study identified security, housing, accommodation, feeding, medication, clothing, education, empowerment, job, and repatriation as the immediate needs of emergency victims in Kumbotso local government area of Kano State. In addition to this and in a study conducted by Aujara, (2018) entitled an examination of community education needs of IDPs in Borno State, Nigeria. The study justified the level of educational attainment; community education needs; and scope of community education programmes for the IDPs living in IDPs Camps in Borno State. These included vocational education, civic and citizenship education, entrepreneurial and environmental education.

The third finding of this study which is the opinions of emergency victims on the relief services provision that were provisions of counselling services; housing; food items; home utensils; clothing materials; building materials; medical facilities; agricultural facilities; capacity building materials, and monetary donation. This finding was similar with the findings discovered during the FGD conducted with the staff of KSEMA.

“The relief services provided to the categories of the emergency victims were money and building materials for the victims of fire outbreak; food items, non-food items, temporary shelters, and medical facilities for both victims of flood and insurgencies; money, food items, and agricultural facilities for the victims of drought and community conflict; artificial legs/arms, walking aids and medical facilities for the victims of automobile accidents and insurgencies as well, and money and clothing materials for the victims of armed robbery.”

The last finding of this study which revealed that the challenges faced by KSEMA in the delivery of relief services to emergency victims were administrative bureaucracy; inadequate funding by the State government; inadequate external funding; lack of communal participation; poor internal donation; poor distribution channel; lack of emergency management agency at the local government level, and frequent occurrence of emergency situations in the State. These challenges were the major challenges identified during the FGD with the staff of KSEMA involved in the provision of relief services to emergency victims. Other challenges mentioned during the FGD were “illiteracy; political affiliations; increase in the rate of the emergency victims; lack of disaster preparedness skills; and communal apathy”. These findings were similarly discovered in a study entitled *Emergency Preparedness and Response to Ibadan Flood Disaster 2011: Implications for Well-being* by Adejuwon & Aina (2014).

Recommendations

The prototype of administration of emergency relief programmes in Kano State suffered management setback especially in ensuring fair distribution of relief materials and lack of provision of what was needed by the emergency victims. However, there were evidences of inadequate facilities to ensure effective administration emergency relief programmes in Kano State. The needed manpower and technical know-how in disaster management are not enough to meet up with the challenges in the State; the failure and inadequacies of administration of emergency relief programmes in the State was partially blamed on the poor funding of the government agencies charged with disaster management in the State; there is evidence of non-enforcement of some environmental management policies in reducing reoccurrence of flood and fire outbreaks; the distribution of the relief materials to the emergency victims not on the basis of their needs and aspirations. Therefore, there is the need for searching for sufficient funding of the programmes

designed for managing emergency situations in case of the occurrences of situations that required emergency responses.

From the conclusion the following recommendation were offered so as to address the challenges through the allocation of resources in a knowledge economy society of Kano State, Nigeria:

- i) Through knowledge economy for manpower and technical know-how, the categories of emergency victims in Kano State should appropriately be identified by the KSEMA taking in to consideration of their peculiarities in dealing with matters related to the provisions of the relief services;
- ii) Through the utilization of knowledge economy, KSEMA should reconsider active community involvement as priority in finding sufficient resources that will cater for the immediate needs of the emergency victims;
- iii) Through knowledge economy KSEMA should also encourage the Kano State Government to establish modern system of the provision of relief services to emergency victims through computerization of emergency victims' data and statuses, and
- iv) Through knowledge economy the Kano State Government should establish agencies that will be charge with the managing of emergency situations at all the local government levels in the State. This will facilitate awareness and easy access to emergency victims at the immediate level of the occurrences of the emergency situations.

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